

Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension among Adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State Nigeria.

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Abstract

The asymptomatic nature of hypertension puts many people at risk of having hypertension without their knowledge that is to say that people with hypertension may not feel symptoms and because of this, this study was designed to determine the knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension among adult in Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State. Four purposes, research questions and hypotheses guided the study and the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significances. A descriptive cross sectional survey design was used for the study; the area of the study was Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State. The population of the study consisted of 615276 adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State. The sample size of the study consisted of 400 adults 191 males and 209 female adults. Multistage sampling procedure was used to determine the sample size also Taro yamane was used to calculate the sample size. The instrument for data collection was a research developed instrument titled knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension test (KARFHT) the validation of the instrument was done by three experts; the reliability of the instrument was established using cronbach Alpha Method and the co-efficient values was 0.76 respectively. Mean and stand deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of study showed that the male had more knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension also younger adults had low knowledge of hypertension; generally, the adults had good knowledge of the associated risk factor of hypertension. Based on this conclusions and recommendation were made; there is need for health education programme on hypertension and this education should be translated to the language the people can understand.

Introduction

Hypertension accounted for 7.5 million and 9.4 million deaths world in 2004 and 2010 respectively. In the year 2000, about 26.4% of the world adult population was living with hypertension and it is projected that this figure will increase to about 29.2% by 2025. Estimated total number of adults with hypertension in high income countries in 2000 was 333 million while it was 654 million in low income Countries, (World Health Organization, 2010).

The burden of hypertension in Abia Senatorial South Zone is more among the elderly population. Despite the high burden of hypertension, most affected persons are not aware of its presence, thus increasing the occurrence of associated complications, particularly among

elderly populations Ong et al, (2007). Most of the adult in Abia South Senatorial Zone are careless of checking their blood pressure; neither do they go for medical checkup, let alone having their personal BP apparatus. Majority of them are preoccupied with their business at the expense of their health. They are indifferent to adherence to lifestyle modifications and to medications.

Unfortunately, most adults in Abia South Senatorial due to ignorance of knowledge of hypertension engage in unhealthy lifestyle such as excessive consumption of alcohol, sedentary lifestyle, excess consumption of sodium intake, tobacco and cigarette smoking, obesity, reduced intake of fruits and vegetables, stress and consumption of foods rich in cholesterol. These unhealthy lifestyle practices have increased the prevalence of hypertension in the zone which culminates into high cases of deaths. Hypertension is one of the problems affecting especially a great portion of the adult population.

Regrettably, most adults due to ignorance of risk to factors and preventive measures of hypertension engage in unhealthy lifestyle such as excessive consumption of alcohol, sedentary lifestyle, excess consumption of alcohol, sedentary lifestyle, excess consumption of sodium intake, tobacco and cigarette smoking, obesity, reduced intake of fruits and vegetables, stress and consumption of food rich in cholesterol. These unhealthy lifestyle practices have increased the prevalence of hypertension in the world including Nigeria, which culminates into high cases of deaths. Hypertension is one of the problems affecting a great portion of the adult population and currently causes one in every eight deaths worldwide, making it the third leading killer disease in the world.

Regarding socio-economic status, especially in terms of level of education, and occupation, low level of education, low income and stressful life occupations have been linked with the prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension. Stressful occupations are characterized by long work hours with workers having little or no time for rest, leisure, and medical checkup and the latter may result in such workers being largely unaware of their health status as it pertains to occult diseases such as hypertension Viera, cohen, Mitchell, Sloane (2008). This situation is common Abia is Abia South Senatorial Zone where majority of the adult are traders and farmers. They are exposed to stress with little regard to knowing their blood pressure status.

It is estimated that hypertension affects about 1 billion people all over the world and it is the main risk factor for many other cardiovascular diseases. The prevalence of hypertension in Nigeria may form a substantial proportion of the total burden in Africa because of the large population of the country currently estimated to be over 170 million WHO to 2004.

Ejike, Ezeanyika and Ugwu (2010) estimated that about one billion adults had hypertension in the year 2010, and the number is expected to rise to 1.56 billion in the year 2025. In addition, hypertension is the commonest non communicable disease in Nigeria with over 4.3 million Nigerians classified as being hypertensive. In Nigeria, many people lose their lives to hypertension. This is not an acceptable situation, considering the fact that hypertension is preventable and manageable to reduce its impact on the health and lives of people in Nigeria.

Despite effective therapies and lifestyle interventions, optimal prevention of hypertension remains a serious health challenge to health professionals especially in most developing

countries like Nigeria and particular Abia South Senatorial Zone. The above background will motivate the researcher towards ascertaining the knowledge of the risk factors of hypertension among adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension among Adult in Abia South senatorial zone in Abia State. Specifically, the study determined:

1. The knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on gender.
2. The knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on age.
3. The knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South senatorial zone Abia State based on education level.
4. The knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on location.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on gender?
2. What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on age?
3. What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South senatorial zone Abia State based on education level?
4. What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone Abia State based on location?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There was no significance difference in the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension between male and female adults in Abia South Senatorial Zone of Abia State.
2. There will be no significance difference in the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension among adults in Abia South senatorial Zone of Abia State based on age.
3. There was no significance difference in the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension among adults in Abia South senatorial Zone of Abia State based on education level.
4. There was no significance difference in the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension among adults in Abia South senatorial Zone of Abia State based on location.

Methods

The research design adopted for this study is the cross-sectional survey design. This study was carried out in Abia South senatorial zone of Abia State. Abia South senatorial zone is one the three senatorial zones in Abia State. The study population was adults (both sexes) aged 20 years and above. The population for the study consisted of 615276. The sample for this study was four hundred (400) adults (191 males and 209 females). To determine the sample size from the population, the sample size formula propounded by Taro Yamane was used. The instrument for data collection was a researcher designed structured instrument on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension Test otherwise called (KARFHT). The data collected was analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 25. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Hypotheses one, four, five and eight were tested using t - Test while Hypotheses two, three, six and seven were tested using ANOVA. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance and appropriate degrees of free

Results and Discussion

Research Question One

What is the knowledge of associated risk factor of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on gender?

Table 1

Mean Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension by Gender of Respondents in Abia South Senatorial Zone

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Remark
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Percentage Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension	male	72	50.00	19.11	Moderate
	female	320	49.17	21.53	Low
	Total	392	49.32	21.09	Low

The results displayed in Table 1 shows that the mean knowledge on associated risk factors of hypertension was 50.00 for male adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia state while the mean knowledge for the females was 49.19. This means that male adults had moderate knowledge, and the females had low knowledge. However, the mean different of 0.83 suggests that male adults in Abia state had slightly higher percentage knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension also the standard deviation of male and female was closer to the central mean with the value of 19.11 and 21.53 .

Research Question Two

What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on Age?

Table 2

Mean Scores on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension by Age of Respondents in Abia South Senatorial Zone

Variable	Age Range	N	Mean	SD	Remak
Percentage Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension	35-45	236	45.57	20.98	Low
	46-55	64	58.33	14.55	Moderate
	56-65	48	52.78	21.56	Moderate
	66 & above	44	52.53	24.48	Moderate
	Total	392	49.32	21.09	Low

Table 2 shows that respondents between 46-55 years had the highest mean knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension as demonstrated by the mean score of 58.33 while those between 35-45 had the lowest mean score (45.57). Those between 56 and 65, and those that were 66 years and above had about the same mean knowledge score (52.78 and 52.53). These mean scores suggests that the youngest category of respondents (35-45) had low knowledge of associated factors of hypertension while others had moderate knowledge all; the standard deviation of the various groups were closer to the central mean.

Research Question Three

What is the knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on education level?

Table 3

Mean Scores on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension by Educational Level of Respondents

Variable	Age Range	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Percentage Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension	No formal education	88	37.88	24.45	Very Low
	Primary education	56	44.44	17.47	Low
	Secondary education	72	46.91	19.93	Low
	Tertiary/university education	176	57.58	17.18	Moderate

Table 3 shows that respondents with no formal education had the lowest mean knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension (Mean =37.88) which suggests low knowledge. On the other hand, those with tertiary/university education had the highest mean knowledge (Mean =57.58) which indicates a moderate knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension. Other respondents with primary and those with secondary education have mean knowledge of 44.44 and 46.91 respectively. This suggests that they had low knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension. The standard deviations of the various groups were closer to the central mean.

Research Question Four

What is the knowledge of associated risk factor of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on location?

Table 4

Mean Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension by Location of Respondents in Abia South Senatorial Zone

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Percentage Score on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension	urban	300	51.70	20.68	Moderate
	rural	92	41.55	20.63	Low
	Total	392	49.32	21.09	Low

Table 4 reveals that respondents living in urban areas had mean knowledge of associated risk factors of hypertension = 51.70 while that of respondents in rural area was 41.55. This indicates that those in urban areas had a moderate knowledge while those in rural areas had a low knowledge of associated risks of hypertension. The standard deviations of the two groups were closer to the central mean.

Research Question Five

What is the knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on gender?

Table 5

Mean Score on Knowledge of Preventive Measures of Hypertension by Gender of Respondents in Abia South Senatorial Zone

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Percentage Score on Preventive Measures of Hypertension	male	72	41.25	17.03	Low
	female	320	32.12	13.93	Very Low
	Total	392	33.80	14.95	Very Low

The mean scores displayed in Table 5 show that the male results had a mean knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension = 41.25 while female respondents had mean knowledge = 32.12. This indicates that while male respondents had low knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension, the females had very low knowledge. The difference in mean scores between the two was 9.13. The standard deviations of the two groups were closer to the central mean.

Research Question six

What is the knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension possessed by adults in Abia south senatorial zone of Abia State based on age?

Table 6

Mean Scores on Knowledge of Associated Risk Factors of Hypertension by Age of Respondents in Abia South Senatorial Zone

Variable	Age Range	N	Mean	SD	Remak
Percentage Score on Knowledge of Preventive Measures of Hypertension	35-45	236	33.54	15.84	Very Low
	46-55	64	38.45	13.21	Very Low
	56-65	48	33.84	9.34	Very Low
	66 & above	44	28.37	15.70	Very Low

Results displayed in Table 6 indicates that respondents between 46-55 years had the highest mean knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension as shown by the mean score of 38.45 while those 66 years and above had the lowest mean score (Mean = 28.37). Those between 35-45, and those between 56 and 65 had almost the same mean knowledge of preventive measures of hypertension (33.54 and 33.84). All the mean scores suggest that all respondents of different age range had very low knowledge of the preventive measures of hypertension. The standard deviations of the various groups were closer to the central mean.

Discussion of the Findings

Knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension, the findings showed that male adults in Abia State had moderate knowledge of the risk factors of hypertension while their female counterpart had how knowledge of the risk factors of hypertension was slightly higher in percentage. When the knowledge of he associated risk factors of hypertension was checked based on their age, the adults between the ages of 46 - 65 years had the highest mean

knowledge as demonstrated by the mean score. Adults between the ages of 25 - 45 years had the lowest mean score. While adults of other age category had modern rate means score on the knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension. Accessing the knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension when considering their level of education, adults with no formal education had the lowest mean knowledge, the adults with tertiary or university education had the highest mean knowledge score; although, the high knowledge was moderate. Adult with primary education also had low knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension but their knowledge was better than that of the no formal education adults. Also when comparing the knowledge of adults in Abia State of the associated risk factor of hypertension checking the location, those adults living in the urban areas, had moderate knowledge of the subject matter while adults living in the rural areas had low knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension. The result of the study was so because of the stressful activity of providing the family as well as meeting up with the society demands. On the other hand, older adult men by age are also more likely to have better knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension because they must have been filled with experience and also have suffered from it for a very long time. The adult men living in the urban area might have the opportunity of listening to education discussion either on the radio or even the office; living in the urban area have given them an opportunity to be more enlightened than adults living in the rural areas. The study was supported by the study conducted by Taha and Bella (2008) that the knowledge of the risk factors was significantly associated with education level. It was also supported by the study of Sarma and Nagaraj (2008) that age also influenced knowledge of the associated risk factors of hypertension. The null hypothesis of no significant differences between male and female adults in Abia State regarding knowledge of the risk factors of hypertension was not rejected.

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